

BioStruct 101136335

Manufacturing process for bio-based fibre-reinforced composite parts for structural applications

Deliverable D0.1 “Boat Manufacturing Process – AMURA”

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1. Objective

1.1 Contributions

All information and deliverable content related to the conventional boat manufacturing process presented in this document were prepared by AMURA.

1.2 Deliverable objective

The objective of this deliverable is to describe the conventional composite boat manufacturing process used by AMURA as a reference within the BioStruct project.

The document presents the reference boat and manufacturing technology, the current material system, and the main stages of the manufacturing process. This information provides the baseline for understanding the existing production process and for identifying the materials and manufacturing steps considered in the transition towards bio-based composite solutions within BioStruct.

2. Reference boat and manufacturing technology

This section describes the reference boat and the conventional manufacturing technology used by AMURA as the baseline for the BioStruct project. The information presented includes the reference boat configuration, the composite manufacturing approach applied in the conventional process, and the current material system used before the transition towards bio-based composite solutions.

2.1 Reference boat

The reference boat considered in this deliverable is based on an existing commercial model manufactured by AMURA. This model was selected as the starting point for the BioStruct demonstrator activities because its geometry, dimensions and current composite construction process provided a representative case study for the transition from conventional glass fibre composites towards bio-based composite solutions.

The original design was based on a small recreational craft with an approximate hull length of 5.99 m and a beam of 2.50 m. The conventional version is manufactured using glass fibre-reinforced composite materials and a hand lay-up production process. The main composite parts considered in the reference manufacturing process are the hull, deck, and internal structural reinforcements, including stringers and frames.

The reference boat was used to identify the main materials, manufacturing stages and process requirements associated with AMURA's conventional production route. This information was used as the baseline for comparison with the bio-based manufacturing approach developed within BioStruct.

2.2 Conventional manufacturing technology

AMURA's conventional boat manufacturing process is based on the hand lay-up of glass fibre-reinforced polymer laminates in open moulds. The main composite components of the reference model, including the hull, deck and internal structural grid, are manufactured separately and subsequently assembled by structural adhesive bonding. The reference boat was originally designed according to this assembly concept in order to reduce additional secondary lamination operations during production.

The conventional moulds are rigid open moulds intended for manual lamination. The process allows the application of gelcoat, the manual positioning of glass fibre reinforcements and the impregnation of the laminate with polyester resin. This manufacturing route is commonly used in boat production due to its flexibility, relatively simple tooling requirements and suitability for complex geometries.

Within the framework of the BioStruct project, the conventional hand lay-up manufacturing route is to be improved through the implementation of vacuum infusion. For this purpose, the original moulds of the reference model are to be adapted, since the conventional mould configuration does not include the peripheral flanges or technical areas required for vacuum bagging, resin distribution lines and vacuum connection points.

Figure 1 : Hull, deck and internal structural grid of the AMURA reference boat.

The implementation of vacuum infusion as a closed-mould process is intended to improve laminate repeatability, optimise resin content control, reduce direct operator exposure to liquid resin and facilitate the processing of the selected bio-based material system under controlled vacuum conditions.

2.3 Current material system

The conventional material system used by AMURA is based on glass fibre reinforcements, polyester resin, marine foam core materials, gelcoat and structural adhesive. The material selection depends on the structural requirements, geometry and function of each area of the boat.

The main conventional materials considered in this deliverable are:

- isophthalic polyester resin,
- glass fibre chopped strand mats,
- glass fibre woven and combined reinforcements,
- marine foam core material,
- polyester gelcoat,
- structural adhesive for assembly operations.

The glass fibre reinforcements are used as the main load-bearing reinforcement system in the conventional laminate. The polyester resin is used as the matrix material for conventional laminate manufacturing. The marine foam core is used in sandwich areas where increased stiffness and reduced weight are required. Gelcoat is applied to the external surfaces to provide

the required surface finish and protection. Structural adhesive is used during the assembly of the main composite parts.

The current material system described in this section represents the conventional reference configuration considered for comparison with the bio-based material system developed within the BioStruct Project.

3. Manufacturing process

The conventional manufacturing process of the reference boat is organised into three main stages: lamination, machining and assembly. These stages cover the production of the main composite components, their dimensional adjustment after demoulding, and the final bonding and assembly operations required to obtain the complete boat structure.

3.1 Lamination process

The lamination process is carried out in rigid open moulds prepared for manual lay-up. Before laminate production, the mould surface is cleaned and prepared with the corresponding release system. Gelcoat is then applied to the mould surface in order to provide the required external finish and surface protection of the final component.

Figure 2: Manual lay-up of glass fibre reinforcements.

After gelcoat curing, the glass fibre reinforcement sequence is manually positioned in the mould according to the laminate configuration defined for each component and area of the boat. The reinforcement system is impregnated with polyester resin by hand lay-up. Consolidation is performed during impregnation in order to promote fibre wet-out, reduce entrapped air and obtain adequate contact between the reinforcement layers.

In sandwich areas, the marine foam core is positioned as part of the laminate sequence. The core is incorporated in the areas where increased stiffness and reduced weight are required, according to the structural and functional requirements of the component. Additional glass fibre layers are applied over the core to close the sandwich configuration and provide laminate continuity.

The laminated components are cured under workshop conditions according to the resin system and internal production requirements. After curing, the components are demoulded and transferred to the machining stage for trimming, adjustment and preparation for assembly.

3.2 Machining

The machining stage includes the cutting, trimming, sanding and drilling operations required after demoulding. These operations are carried out in a dedicated area in order to control dust generation and to separate machining activities from clean lamination and assembly areas.

The main operations include edge trimming, adjustment of bonding areas, opening of required cut-outs, sanding of internal surfaces and preparation of the contact areas for adhesive bonding. The hull, deck and internal structural grid are checked and adjusted to ensure the correct fit between components before final assembly.

Quality control checks are also performed during this stage. The external gelcoat surfaces are inspected to verify that the required surface finish has been achieved and that no visible defects, marks or damage are present. The machined edges, bonding areas and relevant dimensional references are also checked before the components are released for assembly.

3.3 Assembly

The assembly stage is carried out in a clean area separated from machining operations. The hull, deck and internal structural grid are positioned, checked and assembled according to the defined production sequence.

The main joining method is structural adhesive bonding. Bonding areas are prepared before adhesive application in order to promote adequate adhesion between components. The internal structural grid is positioned inside the hull and bonded to the corresponding contact areas. Local manual lamination may be applied where required to reinforce specific joints or to provide structural continuity between components.

After installation of the internal structure, the deck is positioned and bonded to the hull and internal reinforcements. The perimeter joint is then closed according to the conventional assembly procedure. Once the structural assembly has cured, additional fittings, covers, hatches, hardware and customer-specific equipment can be installed according to the final configuration of the boat.

This manufacturing sequence allows the main composite components to be produced separately and subsequently assembled in a controlled manner, reducing the need for extensive secondary lamination during final assembly.

4. Conclusions

The BioStruct project aims to assess the use of bio-based composite materials in structural applications, with particular focus on the replacement of conventional glass fibre-based solutions by natural fibre reinforcements and bio-based resin systems.

For this purpose, the conventional manufacturing process used by AMURA provides the necessary reference baseline for the development of the BioStruct demonstrator. The existing boat construction route, based on glass fibre composites, polyester resin and hand lay-up manufacturing, defines the starting point from which material substitution, process adaptation and structural validation can be addressed.

This baseline allows the technical implications of the new material system to be evaluated in relation to the existing production requirements, including tooling, laminate configuration, handling, assembly and process control.

The information compiled in this deliverable supports the subsequent development activities within BioStruct by establishing a clear reference for comparison between the conventional AMURA manufacturing route and the bio-based composite manufacturing approach proposed in the project.